

XROTOR

X-shaped Radical Offshore Wind Turbine for Overall Cost of Energy Reduction

D8.1

Monthly Reports

 <https://xrotor-project.eu>

 @XROTORProject

April 2024

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Approval

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1	2024/04/30		William Leithead and James Carroll 	

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X-ROTOR Consortium

University of UoS

Delft University of Technology

University College Cork – National University of Ireland, Cork

Fundacion Cener

General Electric Renovables España

Norwegian University of Science and Technology

CENER

NTNU – Trondheim
Norwegian University of
Science and Technology

UCC
Coláiste na hOllscoile Corcaigh, Éire
University College Cork, Ireland

<https://xrotor-project.eu>

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About X-ROTOR

X-ROTOR: “X-shaped Radical Offshore wind Turbine for Overall cost of energy Reduction” is a Horizon 2020 funded project which aims to develop a disruptive new offshore wind turbine concept.

The X-ROTOR project is led by University of UoS (UK) in partnership with Norwegian University of Science and Technology (Norway), Delft University of Technology (Netherlands), University College Cork (Ireland), Fundacion Cener National Renewable Energy Centre (Spain) and GE Renovables España (Spain).

As the effects of climate change are becoming ever more visible, Europe has raised its target for the amount of energy it consumes from renewable sources from the previous goal of 27% to 32% by 2030. Offshore wind energy can play a key role in achieving the EU target and contribute to the required 40% reduction in CO₂ emissions. However, to achieve the previously mentioned targets the cost of offshore wind must be reduced. The X-ROTOR concept provides a direct route to drastically reducing both capital and operating costs of energy from offshore wind.

The project runs for three years from January 2021, during which time, the concept will be developed through a holistic consideration of technical, cost, environmental and socio-economic impact aspects.

If proven feasible, X-ROTOR will, as a disruptive new offshore wind turbine concept, create new opportunities for the European wind energy industry and play an important role maintaining the EU’s position as global technological leader in renewable energy, reducing greenhouse gas emissions and decarbonising the EU economy.

For more information see <https://xrotor-project.eu>

Introduction/Description of the deliverable and its purpose

This deliverable consists of monthly two-page overviews on project activity and progress created by UoS. Each overview was reviewed and signed off by both GE and UoS. This dual sign off shows the industrial partners engaged and continuous role throughout the XROTOR project. This deliverable will be considered successfully complete when the overview is reviewed by GE and emailed to the project coordinator.

List of acronyms

VAWT	Vertical Axis Wind Turbine
HAWT	Horizontal Axis Wind Turbine
PMSG	Permanent Magnet Synchronous Generator
UoS	University of UoS
UCC	University College Cork
NTNU	Norwegian University of Science and Technology
TU Delft	Delft University of Technology
GE	General Electric
CENER	National Renewable Energy Centre
PC	Project Coordinator

Monthly review meeting documents

January 2021 – April 2024 in chronological order.

1 Year 1

1.1 January 2021

Details of meetings

Meeting	Progress Satisfactory	Progress Unsatisfactory	Notes
Kick-off meeting	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	Agenda / Minutes / Actions / Attendees / Presentations – saved in XROTOR SharePoint site
WP1 & 8 x 6 Attendees: Bill Leithead and James Carroll	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	Action planning

Deliverable/Milestone

Submitted for review	Notes	Who?
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	D1.1	UoS
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	MS1	UoS

○ **Signature of Project Lead**

Name: William Leithead

Signature:

Date: 19/02/21

○ **Ratification by GE Partner**

In signing off this form, the representative for the GE partner is confirming that the work is of a standard acceptable to industry or will be, should any action requested be completed.

Name: Jordi Jové Bellot

Signature:

Date: 26/02/21

1.2 February 2021

Details of meetings

Meeting	Progress Satisfactory	Progress Unsatisfactory	Notes
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Consortium	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	Agenda / Minutes / Actions / Attendees / Presentations - saved in XROTOR SharePoint site.
WP1 & 8 x 5 Attendees: Bill Leithead & James Carroll	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Action planning

Deliverable/Milestone

Submitted for review	Notes	Who?
<input type="checkbox"/>	N/A for this month	

○ **Signature of Project Lead**

Name: William Leithead

Signature:

Date: 19/03/21

○ **Ratification by GE Partner**

In signing off this form, the representative for the GE partner is confirming that the work is of a standard acceptable to industry or will be, should any action requested be completed.

Name: Jordi Jové Bellot

Signature:

Date: 26/03/21

1.3 March 2021**Details of meetings**

Meeting	Progress Satisfactory	Progress Unsatisfactory	Notes
Consortium	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Agenda / Minutes / Actions / Attendees / Presentations - saved in XROTOR SharePoint site.
WP1 Attendees: Bill Leithead, James Carroll and Adam Stock	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Data management planning Overview of XROTOR WP work ongoing
WP2, 3, 4 & 5 x 2 Attendees: Bill Leithead, James Carroll and Jordi Jové Bellot	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Planning WP going forward.
WP 1 & 8 x 2 Attendees: Bill Leithead and James Carroll	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Planning

Deliverable/Milestone

Submitted for review	Notes	Who?
☒	D9.1	UCC

○ **Signature of Project Lead**

Name: William Leithead

Signature:

Date: 23/04/21

○ **Ratification by GE Partner**

In signing off this form, the representative for the GE partner is confirming that the work is of a standard acceptable to industry or will be, should any action requested be completed.

Name: Jordi Jové Bellot

Signature:

Date: 30/04/21

1.4 April 2021

Details of meetings

Meeting	Progress Satisfactory	Progress Unsatisfactory	Notes
WP1 & 8 Attendees: Bill Leithead and James Carroll	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Planning • Overview of XROTOR WP work ongoing
WP1 Bill Leithead, James Carroll and Adam Stock	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Data management planning

Deliverable/Milestone

Submitted for review	Notes	Who?
<input type="checkbox"/>	N/A for this month	

○ **Signature of Project Lead**

Name: William Leithead

Signature:

Date: 21/05/21

○ **Ratification by GE Partner**

In signing off this form, the representative for the GE partner is confirming that the work is of a standard acceptable to industry or will be, should any action requested be completed.

Name: Jordi Jové Bellot

Signature:

Date: 28/05/21

1.5 May 2021

Details of meetings

Meeting	Progress Satisfactory	Progress Unsatisfactory	Notes
WP1 Attendees:	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Data management planning

Bill Leithead, James Carroll and Adam Stock			
WP1 & 8 Bill Leithead and James Carroll	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Planning meeting • Review of XROTOR WP work ongoing

Deliverable/Milestone

Submitted for review	Notes	Who?
<input type="checkbox"/>	N/A for this month	

○ **Signature of Project Lead**

Name: William Leithead

Signature:

Date: 18/06/21

○ **Ratification by GE Partner**

In signing off this form, the representative for the GE partner is confirming that the work is of a standard acceptable to industry or will be, should any action requested be completed.

Name: Jordi Jové Bellot

Signature:

Date: 25/06/21

1.6 June 2021**Details of meetings**

Meeting	Progress Satisfactory	Progress Unsatisfactory	Notes
WP4 TMT Attendees: Bill Leithead, James Carroll and Michael Muskulus	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Planning • Milestone due end of month.
WP2 TMT Attendees: Bill Leithead, James Carroll and Carlos Simoa Ferreira	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Planning
WP2, 3 &4 Attendees: Bill Leithead, James Carroll, Jordi Jové Bellot, Michael Muskulus and Carlos Simoa Ferreira	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Design discussion

<p>WP7 & 9 Attendees: Bill Leithead, James Carroll, Jordi Jové Bellot, and Niall Dunphy</p>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Deliverable and milestone due end of month.
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Deliverable/Milestone

Submitted for review	Notes	Who?
☒	D1.4	UoS
☒	D1.7	UoS
☒	D1.8	UCC
☒	MS10	NTNU
☒	D7.1	UCC
☒	D7.9	UCC
☒	MS29	UCC

○ **Signature of Project Lead**

Name: William Leithead

Signature:

Date: 23/07/21

○ **Ratification by GE Partner**

In signing off this form, the representative for the GE partner is confirming that the work is of a standard acceptable to industry or will be, should any action requested be completed.

Name: Jordi Jové Bellot

Signature:

Date: 30/07/21

1.7 July 21

Details of meetings

Meeting	Progress Satisfactory	Progress Unsatisfactory	Notes
WP1 Attendees: Bill Leithead, James Carroll and Adam Stock	☒	☐	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Data management planning

WP5 TMT Attendees: Bill Leithead, James Carroll, David Campos Genoa and Olimpo Anaya-Lara	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Progress discussion on WP5 tasks and deliverable planning
WP6 Attendees: Bill Leithead and James Carroll	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> WP6 not yet started but planning discussion was held.

Deliverable/Milestone

Submitted for review	Notes	Who?
<input type="checkbox"/>	N/A for this month	

○ **Signature of Project Lead**

Name: William Leithead

Signature:

Date: 20/08/21

○ **Ratification by GE Partner**

In signing off this form, the representative for the GE partner is confirming that the work is of a standard acceptable to industry or will be, should any action requested be completed.

Name: Jordi Jové Bellot

Signature:

Date: 27/08/21

1.8 August 2021

Details of meetings

Meeting	Progress Satisfactory	Progress Unsatisfactory	Notes
WP1 & 8 x 3 Attendees: Bill Leithead and James Carroll	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Planning meetings • Review of XROTOR WP work ongoing
WP4 Attendees: Bill Leithead, James Carroll and Michael Muskulus	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • WP planning and hiring discussion

Deliverable/Milestone

Submitted for review	Notes	Who?
<input type="checkbox"/>	N/A for this month	

Signature of Project Lead

Name: William Leithead

Signature:

Date: 24/09/21

○ **Ratification by GE Partner**

In signing off this form, the representative for the GE partner is confirming that the work is of a standard acceptable to industry or will be, should any action requested be completed.

Name: Jordi Jové Bellot

Signature:

Date: 01/10/21

1.9 September 2021

Details of meetings

Meeting	Progress Satisfactory	Progress Unsatisfactory	Notes
WP1 & 8	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	• Planning meeting

Attendees: Bill Leithead and James Carroll			<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Review of XROTOR WP work ongoing
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Deliverable/Milestone

Submitted for review	Notes	Who?
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	D2.1	TU Delft
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	D4.1	NTNU
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	D9.2	UoS

○ **Signature of Project Lead**

Name: William Leithead

Signature:

Date: 22/10/21

○ **Ratification by GE Partner**

In signing off this form, the representative for the GE partner is confirming that the work is of a standard acceptable to industry or will be, should any action requested be completed.

Name: Jordi Jové Bellot

Signature:

Date: 29/10/21

1.10 October 2021

Details of meetings

Meeting	Progress Satisfactory	Progress Unsatisfactory	Notes
WP1 & 8 Attendees: Bill Leithead and James Carroll	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Planning meeting • Review of XROTOR WP work ongoing

Deliverable/Milestone

Submitted for review	Notes	Who?
<input type="checkbox"/>	N/A for this month	

○ **Signature of Project Lead**

Name: William Leithead

Signature:

Date: 19/11/21

○ **Ratification by GE Partner**

In signing off this form, the representative for the GE partner is confirming that the work is of a standard acceptable to industry or will be, should any action requested be completed.

Name: Jordi Jové Bellot

Signature:

Date: 26/11/21

1.11 November 2021

Details of meetings

Meeting	Progress Satisfactory	Progress Unsatisfactory	Notes
WP4 x 2 Attendees: Bill Leithead, James Carroll and Michael Muskulus	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> WP hiring and planning discussion

WP2 Attendees: Bill Leithead, James Carroll and Carlos Simoa- Ferreira	☒	☐	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • WP2 planning discussion
WP5 Attendees: Bill Leithead, James Carroll and David Campos- Genoa	☒	☐	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • WP 5 planning discussion
WP2, 3 & 4 Attendees: Bill Leithead, James Carroll, Michael Muskulus and Carlos Simoa- Ferreira	☒	☐	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Alignment meeting for WP2,3 and 4
WP7 & 9 TMT Attendees: Bill Leithead, James Carroll and Niall Dunphy	☒	☐	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Update on WP7 and WP9 from UCC
PC meeting Attendees: Bill Leithead, James Carroll and Jordi Jové Bellot	☒	☐	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Catch up with management team on project progress.

Deliverable/Milestone

Submitted for review	Notes	Who?
<input type="checkbox"/>	N/A for this month	

○ **Signature of Project Lead**

Name: William Leithead

Signature:

Date: 10/12/21

○ **Ratification by GE Partner**

In signing off this form, the representative for the GE partner is confirming that the work is of a standard acceptable to industry or will be, should any action requested be completed.

Name: Jordi Jové Bellot

Signature:

Date: 17/12/21

1.12 December 2021

Details of meetings

Meeting	Progress Satisfactory	Progress Unsatisfactory	Notes
Executive Management	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Agenda / Minutes / Actions / Attendees / Presentations - saved in XROTOR SharePoint site.
WP1 & 8 x 4 Attendees: Bill Leithead and James Carroll	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> 1st year deliverable planning meetings XROTOR WP work ongoing

Deliverable/Milestone

Submitted for review	Notes	Who?
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	MS4	TU Delft
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	D1.2	UoS
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	D1.9	UoS
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	D2.2	TU Delft
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	MS11	NTNU
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	D5.1	UoS
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	MS15	UoS
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	D7.1	UCC
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	D7.2	UCC
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	D7.5	UCC

<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	D9.3	UoS
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	D10.3	UoS

○ **Signature of Project Lead**

Name: William Leithead

Signature:

Date: 14/01/22

○ **Ratification by GE Partner**

In signing off this form, the representative for the GE partner is confirming that the work is of a standard acceptable to industry or will be, should any action requested be completed.

Name: Jordi Jové Bellot

Signature:

Date: 21/01/22

2 Year 2

2.1 January 2022

Details of meetings

Meeting	Progress Satisfactory	Progress Unsatisfactory	Notes
PC meeting Attendees: Bill Leithead, James Carroll and Jordi Jové Bellot	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Update on shortlisting and interviews for Project Administrator. Monthly update on progress.

Deliverable/Milestone

Submitted for review	Notes	Who?
<input type="checkbox"/>	N/A for this month	

○ **Signature of Project Lead**

Name: William Leithead

Signature:

Date: 18/02/22

○ **Ratification by GE Partner**

In signing off this form, the representative for the GE partner is confirming that the work is of a standard acceptable to industry or will be, should any action requested be completed.

Name: Jordi Jové Bellot

Signature:

Date: 25/02/22

2.2 February 2022

Details of meetings

Meeting	Progress Satisfactory	Progress Unsatisfactory	Notes
PC MEETING Attendees: Bill Leithead, James Carroll and Jordi Jové Bellot	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Monthly update on progress.

Deliverable/Milestone

Submitted for review	Notes	Who?
<input type="checkbox"/>	N/A for this month	

○ **Signature of Project Lead**

Name: William Leithead

Signature:

Date: 18/03/22

○ **Ratification by GE Partner**

In signing off this form, the representative for the GE partner is confirming that the work is of a standard acceptable to industry or will be, should any action requested be completed.

Name: Jordi Jové Bellot

Signature:

Date: 25/03/22

2.3 March 2022

Details of meetings

Meeting	Progress Satisfactory	Progress Unsatisfactory	Notes
PC MEETING Attendees:	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Introduction to new Project administrator. • Monthly update on progress.

Bill Leithead, James Carroll, Jordi Jove Bellot and Nicola Baxter			<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Access discussed with GE for SharePoint site, and issues with Firewall. JJB will investigate this. • Discussed Consortium technical meeting online. Dates to go out to members with doodle poll.
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Deliverable/Milestone

Submitted for review	Notes	Who?
☒	MS8	UoS
☒	D3.2	UoS
☒	MS12	NTNU
☒	MS16	UoS
☒	D4.2	NTNU

○ **Signature of Project Lead**

Name: William Leithead

Signature:

Date: 22/04/22

○ **Ratification by GE Partner**

In signing off this form, the representative for the GE partner is confirming that the work is of a standard acceptable to industry or will be, should any action requested be completed.

Name: Jordi Jové Bellot

Signature:

Date: 29/04/22

2.4 April 2022

Details of meetings

Meeting	Progress Satisfactory	Progress Unsatisfactory	Notes
<p>TMT WP4 Attendees: Bill Leithead, James Carroll, Michael Muskulus, Jordi Jové Bellot, Peter Jamieson and Nicola Baxter</p>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Adriana working with feasibility design for jacket but too heavy at 9000 tonnes. Further modelling work needed. • Several models ongoing with WP2, WP4 and UoS – need to make sure working with assumption that all are consistent. • Important in choosing operating strategy: trimming to reduce loads, changing tip-speed ratio and avoid peak-loads. • Meeting needed between WP4, WP3 and WP2. • WP4 to Look at blade – inspect structural properties. • Focus more on optimal structure design. • Accurate loads; operational strategies; initial design of controller all needed after the summer. • WP4 could be the first WP to look at 3 blades but BL not keen. Wants to keep scope on 2 bladed.
<p>TMT WP2 Attendees: Bill Leithead, James Carroll, Carlos Simoa Ferreira, Beatriz</p>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Meeting needed for combined WP2, 3 & 4 in next few weeks. • Secondary rotor is ready to add with primary and start simulations. • Multibody analysis needed. • Definition of primary rotor – 5m-7m bend (pre-stressed)

Mendez Lopez, Jordi Jové Bellot and Nicola Baxter			
TMT WP6/3 Attendees: Bill Leithead, James Carroll, Jordi Jové Bellot and Nicola Baxter	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	Set up LCoE model to allow for sensitivity analysis.
TMT WP7/9 Attendees: Bill Leithead, James Carroll, Jordi Jové Bellot, Niall Dunphy and Nicola Baxter	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Focus group on Isle of Islay – contact in Energy Trust to take forward. • ND will contact Grant Allen re further Economics from D7.2 • Website will include deliverables; content from workshops; press release; social media links; blogs; activities and publications. • Reminder that project number needs to be in publications. Accepted ones need to go up onto SharePoint. • JJB confirmed Consortium meeting can go ahead at GE in Barcelona.
TMT leads Attendees: Bill Leithead, James Carroll, Jordi Jové Bellot and Nicola Baxter	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • EEE XROTOR SharePoint site updated by NB and invite sent out. JJB having issues and going to speak to IT at GE. • Presentation template has been uploaded. • Looked at dates for mid-term review for Barcelona in September.

Deliverable/Milestone

Submitted for review	Notes	Who?
<input type="checkbox"/>	N/A for this month	

○ **Signature of Project Lead**

Name: William Leithead

Signature:

Date: 20/05/22

○ **Ratification by GE Partner**

In signing off this form, the representative for the GE partner is confirming that the work is of a standard acceptable to industry or will be, should any action requested be completed.

Name: Jordi Jové Bellot

Signature:

Date: 27/05/22

2.5 May 2022

Details of meetings

Meeting	Progress Satisfactory	Progress Unsatisfactory	Notes
TMT WP5 Attendees:	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	Discussions around WP5 activity including: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Modify when it is partially loaded as it's being tested on full load. • Minimum rotor speed.

Bill Leithead, James Carroll, David Campos, Jordi Jové Bellot and Nicola Baxter			<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Trim the peaks off rotor speed. • Plot from generator – power v angle • Low frequency – increase wider air gaps.
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Deliverable/Milestone

Submitted for review	Notes	Who?
<input type="checkbox"/>	N/A for this month	

○ **Signature of Project Lead**

Name: William Leithead

Signature:

Date: 24/06/22

○ **Ratification by GE Partner**

In signing off this form, the representative for the GE partner is confirming that the work is of a standard acceptable to industry or will be, should any action requested be completed.

Name: Jordi Jové Bellot

Signature:

Date: 01/07/22

2.6 June 2022

Details of meetings

Meeting	Progress Satisfactory	Progress Unsatisfactory	Notes
Consortium x 2	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Agenda / Minutes / Actions / Attendees / Presentations - saved in XROTOR SharePoint site.
Post Consortium Attendees: Bill Leithead, James Carroll, Jordi Jové Bellot and Nicola Baxter	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Quarterly meeting to be set up between WP2, 3&4 to assist in communication. Also encourage ad hoc meetings between WP's. • Concern over dynamic analysis of system. WP4 to focus on this. • Proposal of researchers attending other institutions to see share their work.
PC meeting Attendees: Bill Leithead, James Carroll, Jordi Jové Bellot and Nicola Baxter	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Discussion regarding sensitivity data. • Laurie's work with TU Delft – thrust on rotor. • CoE – O&M costs a key input. • Cohesion with different WPs – joint papers, workshops.

Deliverable/Milestone

Submitted for review	Notes	Who?
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	MS3	UoS
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	MS5	TU Delft
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	D1.5	UoS

<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	D2.3	TU Delft
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	D3.3	UoS
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	D7.11	UCC
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	D9.4	UoS / UCC

○ **Signature of Project Lead**

Name: William Leithead

Signature:

Date: 22/07/22

○ **Ratification by GE Partner**

In signing off this form, the representative for the GE partner is confirming that the work is of a standard acceptable to industry or will be, should any action requested be completed.

Name: Jordi Jové Bellot

Signature:

Date: 29/07/22

2.7 July 2022

Details of meetings

Meeting	Progress Satisfactory	Progress Unsatisfactory	Notes
Executive Management	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Agenda / Minutes / Actions / Attendees / Presentations - saved in XROTOR SharePoint site.

Deliverable/Milestone

Submitted for review	Notes	Who?
<input type="checkbox"/>	N/A for this month	

○ **Signature of Project Lead**

Name: William Leithead

Signature:

Date: 19/08/22

○ **Ratification by GE Partner**

In signing off this form, the representative for the GE partner is confirming that the work is of a standard acceptable to industry or will be, should any action requested be completed.

Name: Jordi Jové Bellot

Signature:

Date: 26/08/22

2.8 August 2022

Details of meetings

Meeting	Progress Satisfactory	Progress Unsatisfactory	Notes
WP2 Attendees: Bill Leithead, James Carroll and Simon Watson	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> D1.3 Data Management Plan – issues to resolve. Feed this resolution back to Adam Stock.
Independent Advisory Board x 2	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Agenda / Minutes / Actions / Attendees saved in other paperwork.
PO Meeting Attendees: Bill Leithead, Jordi Jové Bellot and Nicola Baxter	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Consortium meeting in GE will be on MS Teams for those unable to attend in person. JJB will provide lunch, tea etc. Agenda confirmed for Consortium meeting.

Deliverable/Milestone

Submitted for review	Notes	Who?
☑	D2.4	TU Delft

○ **Signature of Project Lead**

Name: William Leithead

Signature:

Date: 23/09/22

○ **Ratification by GE Partner**

In signing off this form, the representative for the GE partner is confirming that the work is of a standard acceptable to industry or will be, should any action requested be completed.

Name: Jordi Jové Bellot

Signature:

Date: 30/09/22

2.9 September 2022

Details of meetings

Meeting	Progress Satisfactory	Progress Unsatisfactory	Notes
Individual IAB x 2 Attendees: Bill Leithead, James Carroll, John Olav Tande and Chris Spruce	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Members agreed to have individual meetings as they missed either Part I or II of the general meetings with information of XROTOR, and more information regarding the project.
Consortium Meeting, Barcelona	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Agenda / Minutes / Actions / Attendees saved in other paperwork.

Deliverable/Milestone

Submitted for review	Notes	Who?
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	D2.5	CENER
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	D2.6	CENER
<input type="checkbox"/>	MS22 – agreed by PO to submit end December 2022	UCC

○ **Signature of Project Lead**

Name: William Leithead

Signature:

Date: 21/10/22

o **Ratification by GE Partner**

In signing off this form, the representative for the GE partner is confirming that the work is of a standard acceptable to industry or will be, should any action requested be completed.

Name: Jordi Jové Bellot

Signature:

Date: 28/10/22

2.10 October 2022

Details of meetings

Meeting	Progress Satisfactory	Progress Unsatisfactory	Notes
WP5 Attendees: Bill Leithead, James Carroll, David Campos-Gaona, Seyed Mortazavizadeh	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Discussion regarding generator loads / limitations.

and Reza Yazdanpanah			
TMT WP5: Bill Leithead, James Carroll, David Campos-Gaona, Olimpo Anaya-Lara, Jordi Jové Bellot and Nicola Baxter	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Olimpo will email Jordi with information for Ramon of GE, with observations regarding generator loads. • WP4 – MM looking at operational strategy and taking model in 2-step approach. • WP7 – noise profile and tip speeds discussed
WP7 Attendees: Bill Leithead, James Carroll, Peter Deeney and Nicola Baxter	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Discussion around NB attending Islay with UCC to offer administration support and non-technical presentation to focus group. Agreed. • No model available yet to travel to conferences, will be ready for final events. • Ethics, briefing note and focus group guide – docs to be uploaded onto SharePoint for BL to review.
WP2,3 & 4 Attendees: Bill Leithead, James Carroll, Michael Muskulus, Carlos Simoa Ferreira, Beatriz Mendez Lopez, Laurie Morgan, David Bensason, Daniele Ragni, Francesco Avallone and Yan Wu	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Follow-up meeting to approve alignment on the aerodynamic elements of the different WPs.

<p>TMT WP4 Attendees: Bill Leithead, James Carroll, Michael Muskulus, Jordi Jové Bellot and Nicola Baxter</p>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<p>WP4 discussions included:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Effect of reducing loads – cycles by half, structure weigh goes down. This has been submitted for Deepwind conference. • Discussion on what’s driving the design of the loads in jacket • Dynamics/harmonics – 7s with 2 load cycles – damage at 20-30% • Aeroelastic properties being looked at in November. • Primary rotor and structure – need to be investigated. • No aerodynamic dampening • Lack of control on the oscillation – change pitch and loads • WP2 looking for agreement with data – sensitivity study.
<p>TMT WP6 Attendees: Bill Leithead, James Carroll and Peter Jamieson</p>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • New researcher starting full time in November who will take WP6 work forward. • Next milestone and deliverable due at end of January 2023. • Understand, review and sense check the model adjusted by Callum. Make changes where necessary. (Milestone achieved) • Write report on the above to complete deliverable due at end of Jan. • Post Jan, paper on the above areas. Focus turns to working with UCC for CoE modelling and interfacing with UCC CoE model.

Deliverable/Milestone

Submitted for review	Notes	Who?
<input type="checkbox"/>	N/A for this month	

○ **Signature of Project Lead**

Name: William Leithead

Signature:

Date: 18/11/22

○ **Ratification by GE Partner**

In signing off this form, the representative for the GE partner is confirming that the work is of a standard acceptable to industry or will be, should any action requested be completed.

Name: Jordi Jové Bellot

Signature:

Date: 25/11/22

2.11 November 2022

Details of meetings

Meeting	Progress Satisfactory	Progress Unsatisfactory	Notes
TMT WP2 Bill Leithead, James Carroll, Jordi Jové Bellot, Beatriz Mendez, Carlos Simoa Ferreira and Nicola Baxter	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Reporting on the aerodynamic benchmark – no update but running through at the moment– due end of December. BL reiterated need for this ASAP. • Good progress on all other fronts. • Deliverables due end of December are on schedule. • Discussion on performance of turbine within a farm offshore with wake calculations. • Suggestion of visit to Delft around time of Deepwind to see wind tunnel with primary and secondary rotors. • Noise analysis in progress. Need to contact UCC for a meeting. • JJB asked re acoustic noise – machinery noise and everything together?

			<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ Insulate to help with noise but it's not built into project. • Looking for high quality mesh that is computationally affordable. • JC looking for a scaled model with tip rotors for WESC in May? CSC positive this will be ready.
<p>MT WP7&9 Bill Leithead, James Carroll, Niall Dunphy, Jordi Jové Bellot and Nicola Baxter</p>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Social analysis – engaging / workshop in Islay/ contrast with no renewable energy. • Economic analysis. ND to meet Grant Allen (UoS) early 2023. • LCoE due end of January 2023 with Fiona (UCC) • Energy end of July 2023, also with Fiona. • LC03 – timetable a bit late – using interim results. <p>Job creation – input/output model; EU economy i.e. Irish/Spanish – explore early 2023.</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Environmental analysis: engaging at moment out in the field. • D7.3/7.6 – issues due to getting public to engage due to Covid pandemic. • The Website is slow to load. ND will investigate this. ○ Deliverables to go onto website. ○ Link from website – community and file depository. • Press release? ASAP – electronic news on website. • ND has sent templates to Consortium for both Deliverables and presentations. • Ask from EU PO regarding Comms. ND – Comms person in UCC is putting up regular activities. • ND contacting consortium regarding dissemination of public deliverables. • Meeting with BL / JC / ND to discuss what can and can't go up on the website, and D9.5 event end of project – publicising it.
<p>IAB individual Una Brosnan Anurag Gupta John Olav Tande Chris Spruce Tim Camp</p>			<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • IAB members agreed to look over questions and have individual meeting to discuss. They engaged with this very well and there is a report with all the information gathered through transcripts of the meetings.

Deliverable/Milestone

Submitted for review	Notes	Who?
<input type="checkbox"/>	N/A for this month	

○ **Signature of Project Lead**

Name: William Leithead

Signature:

Date: 9/12/22

○ **Ratification by GE Partner**

In signing off this form, the representative for the GE partner is confirming that the work is of a standard acceptable to industry or will be, should any action requested be completed.

Name: Jordi Jové Bellot

Signature:

Date: 16/12/22

2.12 December 2022**Details of meetings**

Meeting	Progress Satisfactory	Progress Unsatisfactory	Notes
TMT WP9 Attendees: Bill Leithead, James Carroll,	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Dissemination plan, discussion
Executive Management Attendees: Bill Leithead, James Carroll, Michael Muskulus, Jordi Jové Bellot, Niall Dunphy and Beatriz Mendez	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Agenda / Minutes / Actions / Attendees saved in other paperwork.

Deliverable/Milestone

Submitted for review	Notes	Who?
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	D1.3	UoS
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	D5.2	UoS
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	D9.5	UoS
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	D7.3	UCC
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	D7.6	UCC

<input type="checkbox"/>	MS22 – agreed by PO to submit end December 2022	UCC
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	MS6	TU Delft
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	MS13	NTNU

○ **Signature of Project Lead**

Name: William Leithead

Signature:

Date: 13/01/23

○ **Ratification by GE Partner**

In signing off this form, the representative for the GE partner is confirming that the work is of a standard acceptable to industry or will be, should any action requested be completed.

Name: Jordi Jové Bellot

Signature:

Date: 20/01/23

3 Year 3

3.1 January 2023

Details of meetings

Meeting	Progress Satisfactory	Progress Unsatisfactory	Notes
TMT WP2, 3 & 4 Attendees: Bill Leithead, James Carroll, Carlos Simoa Ferreira, Michael Muskulus, Jordi Jové Bellot	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Benchmark needed – PhD students working on this. Old model higher performance. Blade pitch changes things. 2d/3d – not much impact on controller. This will impact on WP4 issue with loads.
Consortium Attendees: Bill Leithead, James Carroll, Carlos Simoa Ferreira, Simon Watson, Jordi Jové Bellot, Olimpo Anaya-Lara, David Campos-Gaona and Nicola Baxter	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Agenda / Minutes / Actions / Attendees saved in other paperwork.

Deliverable/Milestone

Submitted for review	Notes	Who?
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	MS19	UoS

<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	D6.1	UoS
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○ **Signature of Project Lead**

Name: William Leithead

Signature:

Date: 17/02/23

○ **Ratification by GE Partner**

In signing off this form, the representative for the GE partner is confirming that the work is of a standard acceptable to industry or will be, should any action requested be completed.

Name: Jordi Jové Bellot

Signature:

Date: 24/02/23

3.2 February 2023

Details of meetings

Meeting	Progress Satisfactory	Progress Unsatisfactory	Notes
PC meeting Attendees: Bill Leithead, Jordi Jové Bellot and Nicola Baxter	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Confirmed that D6.1 and MS19 were submitted on 31st January. • JJB will expect a link to SharePoint to review documents. • Possibility of JJB joining Consortium end of April in Copenhagen with the WindEurope Conference but not guaranteed.
TMT WP7&9 Attendees: Bill Leithead, Niall Dunphy and Nicola Baxter	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • D7.2 Slow recruitment for economic person to take forward this work for XROTOR. Preparatory work is ongoing, and ND hopefully there will be someone in this position in next few months. ND will meet with Grant Allen and Jack Williamson in UoS to discuss economics. • D7.3: Using outputs from WP2 acoustic models for impact on birds. • Life-cycle analysis is being taken forward – information needed from WP 4&5 – materials etc. • D7.1 is progressing well; repeat of last year’s engagement on Islay and professional aspect will be gained with short surveys in person at conferences i.e. WindEurope, WESC etc. BL offered help of participants going to WindEurope for XROTOR to help with interviewing people. NB to check who is attending. • ND liaising with James Carroll regarding WP6. • WP9 outputs have increased with additions to social media and a news addition to the website coming shortly. ND will contact Work Package (WP) leads as looking for inputs to the website. A short video clip will be gained from each WP – this will happen at WESC in May and done on an ad hoc basis.

<p>TMT WP4 Attendees: Bill Leithead, Michael Muskulus, James Carroll, Jordi Jové Bellot and Nicola Baxter</p>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • MM confirmed again that each presentation at Deepwind can submit a paper. Email sent to consortium 07.02.23. • Adrianna working on the reduction of mass and why it's linear. They are running tests looking at optimisation. They have been in contact with Mehrad in looking at blades and can't find the error but there is still a difference in mass between the original study and now. It is thought this could be the difference in the software. • There is a reduction in amplitudes of 25% with latest analysis. • The aerodynamic benchmark has an impact on loads – lessening the dampening. Laurie is going to work on this and report back to MM. The dynamics of the jacket will be lower. • What kind of pile being used will change the frequency of the loads.
<p>TMT WP2 Attendees: Bill Leithead, James Carroll, Carlos Simoa Ferreira, Beatrix Mendez, Jordi Jové Bellot and Nicola Baxter</p>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • CSF confirmed that he's confident that future deliverables will be on time. • They're progressing with writing up the benchmark. • Taking forward the aero-elastic model of XROTOR. • Last week they experimented with the tip rotor – measuring the wake with changing the pitch and will publish data on this. BL commented that the effect on wake can only be done with windfarm modelling. He also wonders if individual pitching will be cost effective. <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ They need to consider noise and higher frequencies, the ranges with greatest impact. ▪ CSF to arrange meeting with WP7 to discuss noise. • BM would like a meeting with WP4 to discuss structural modelling. NB to arrange with BL and JC.
<p>TMT WP3 Attendees: Bill Leithead, James Carroll, Jordi Jové Bellot and Nicola Baxter</p>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • BL confirmed that Mehrad has been working on the mechanical aspects of the generator. Dealing with the cooling without introducing fins. He is writing this up. • They're looking at blades of secondary rotor to passively generate cooling with a pump in hub for easy access. • No implication on control because of secondary rotors. • BJJ asked questions relating to being able to stop the primary rotor quickly. BL would hope the pitch would help to slow it and the function of the secondary rotors. Aerodynamic dampening is being worked on for WP4 – reduction in loads and wind speeds. The aerodynamic measurement is needed for the operation strategy.

<p>TMT WP5 Attendees: Bill Leithead, James Carroll, Jordi Jové Bellot, David Campos Genoa, Olimpo Anyà-Lara and Nicola Baxter</p>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Need to define weight <10t – how flexible can we go? • Terminal analysis – metal plate for cooling; water drop structure; hollow structure in blades; reverse and have magnets on starter; magnets on outside. • Efficiency is good – magnets not main source of heat. • Meeting with BL, DCG and researchers – booked for early March. • Quantity size and material from other WPs needed – also scaling up in size. • Laurie working on control for power electronics – results due this week. • JC will be in contact with DCG regarding a literature review for vessel usage. • Meeting to set up with WP4 to talk about the interdependencies between WPs. • DCG to provide Mehrad a life-cycle analysis this week.
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Deliverable/Milestone

Submitted for review	Notes	Who?
<input type="checkbox"/>	N/A for this month	

○ **Signature of Project Lead**

Name: William Leithead

Signature:

Date: 17/03/23

○ **Ratification by GE Partner**

In signing off this form, the representative for the GE partner is confirming that the work is of a standard acceptable to industry or will be, should any action requested be completed.

Name: Jordi Jové Bellot

Signature:

Date: 24/03/23

3.3 March 2023

Details of meetings

Meeting	Progress Satisfactory	Progress Unsatisfactory	Notes
<p>TMT WP7/9 Attendees: Bill Leithead, James Carroll, Niall Dunphy and Nicola Baxter Apologies: Jordi Jové Bellot & Peter Jamieson</p>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • WP7: Going well with planning on track. Reaching Stornoway for the next workshop as UCC have contact here, also Malin Head in Rep. of Ireland. Looking at one further perhaps Netherlands or Spain. • Decision still to be confirmed for WindEurope and whether attending conference or exhibition hall – students from UoS may be needed and ND will confirm asap. • D7.2: ND spoke to GA and there is an issue with the timeline for 7.7 and 7.9. Going to meet in person to discuss further. An extension will most likely be required and permission from EU PO sought for this. This is due to the delay in resources for economics at UCC. • D7.3: ND passing to the team regarding BL concerns over frequency of noise for birds and not just Db testing. • WP9: Progressing well. Some added stories up on the website. • Email out to consortium members for weekly tweets put together for the next month. UoS due tomorrow with ideas presented to ND which he agreed with. • Publications still need to be gathered from each institute.

			<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Discussion around end of project event is needed to forward plan. Meeting in person when ND comes to meet GA and team. • BL suggested joining with event for other projects funded by EU H2020, which are ending this year and put something on in Europe.
<p>TMT WP4 Attendees: Bill Leithead, James Carroll, Michael Muskulus and Nicola Baxter Apologies: Jordi Jové Bellot</p>	☒	☐	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Adriana and Roberto from CENER have been looking at the mast and need to get more information from Mehrad. • Stress cycles etc. are linear, which is good news. • Adrianna looking at 3 bladed machines, which floating would need. She got the loads from Carlos. Damage is reduced by a factor of 8 and the tip speed is lower. • Nearly finished pile sizing and a paper will be finished by the end of the month. • Questions raised for how to design cross bar/bearing. MM asked about hollow shaft? Transformer needs to be between the bearings. Depends on dimensions – strong locking mechanism. Rotary transformer no optimal idea. <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ Better for access – 500K euros could be saved with no jack-up vessel. • MM will look at main bearing with boundary conditions and estimate of mast. • JC to send MM paper on vessels including dynamic loading on crane.
<p>TMT WP6 Attendees: Bill Leithead, James Carroll and Nicola Baxter Apologies: Jordi Jové Bellot</p>	☒	☐	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • WP 6 Milestone and Deliverable completed and submitted for end of Jan Deadline • O&M model now captures the unique characteristics of the XROTOR concept. • Some case studies and sensitivity analyses have been completed. (Depending on other tasks, we can complete more sensitivity analyses as requested by WPs) • DeepWind paper deadline for Mid-March, Fraser currently working on Bill recommended changes to that. • Fraser carrying out review of vessel capability for WP5 and for project in general • Upcoming Milestones and Deliverables: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ July: CoE of X-Rotor Concept modelled ○ October: CoE of existing turbines modelled and compared to X-Rotor CoE • Whilst both of the above are UCC deliverables, UoS working very closely on these. • UCCs staff on WP6 (Fiona) is starting in April. Time is tight so engagement has started already (Communicated O&M model outputs etc.)

			<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • April: Fraser and Fiona working together to ensure O&M model and LCoE model can be interfaced correctly • May, June and July: will involve defining LCoE cases for analysis, estimating inputs and getting inputs from partners to model LCoE for July deliverable.
<p>TMT WP2 Attendees: Bill Leithead, Carlos Simoa Ferreira, Peter Jamieson and Nicola Baxter Apologies: James Carroll and Beatrix Mendez</p>	☒	☐	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Benchmark progressing well, in fact nearly finished. • Beatriz is working with new meshes and in contact with MM of WP4 regarding structural model – multibody analysis. • Currently preparing wind tunnel studies for the acoustic work, small scale rotor and blade – aeroacoustic measurements. • BL discussed CENER issue with the power output not matching with only 3.2megawatts, whereas CSF is getting 6.4megawatts. As this is half, CSF says to consider this is one blade and not two, which his figure is for. BL will go back to BM with this information.
<p>TMT WP5 Attendees: Bill Leithead, James Carroll, David Campos- Genoa and Olimpo Anaya- Lara</p>	☒	☐	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Revise the design of outer rotor PMSG for heat dissipation requirements. No need to optimize fully, just get a picture of the implications of having such system. • Data regarding maximum carrying capacity of vessels for offshore wind farms will be requested to James and compared against weight of current generator designs. • Keep in touch with Structures WP and update them about space requirements for the Xrotor tower.
<p>WP9 Attendees: Bill Leithead, James Carroll and Niall Dunphy</p>	☒	☐	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Plan A: Extension and WindEurope – Jan 2024. <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ◦ James/Bill to email all WP leads about extension. James to reach out to PO after we hear back from WP leads. • Plan B: IET RPG – Glasgow and Shanghai. <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ◦ James to email David about possibility of event. • Plan C or additional event anyway: Brussels EU event. <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ◦ Bill to reach out to other EU funded projects in our area. • Niall to reach out to all WP leads to find out what have people done and what are people are planning on doing in terms of publications and conferences.

			<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • WESC: WP leads will be asked to do a short video. Niall to circulate questions beforehand. • Model for conferences. Bill and James to discuss • Pop up banner/ - Niall to arrange.
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Deliverable/Milestone

Submitted for review	Notes	Who?
<input type="checkbox"/>	N/A for this month	

○ **Signature of Project Lead**

Name: William Leithead

Signature:

Date: 21/04/23

○ **Ratification by GE Partner**

In signing off this form, the representative for the GE partner is confirming that the work is of a standard acceptable to industry or will be, should any action requested be completed.

Name: Jordi Jové Bellot

Signature:

Date: 28/04/23

3.4 April 2023

Details of meetings

Meeting	Progress Satisfactory	Progress Unsatisfactory	Notes
<p>TMT WP7/9 Attendees: Bill Leithead, James Carroll, Niall Dunphy, Peter Jamieson and Nicola Baxter</p>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • WP7 - Two case economic case studies in progress. Grant doing macro study with UK wide deployment and UCC covering Ireland/EU and looking at bottom-up research for employment. • An extension is required for D7.2 - ND will send an email to JC and BL with information to put to the PO. • Staffing issue has been resolved. • D7.3 is proceeding as planned. Work being one on LCoE. • WP9 – Recruiting colleagues in UCC to take work forward at WESC. • 2 researchers are going to WindEurope and will work in the Exhibition Hall gathering input from industry professionals. • Banner is being made now and can be made available should it be needed for any events. • JC explained about using the Royal Academy of Engineers in London as a possible final event option. This given a wider audience outside of Wind. • UCC don't for see any extension needed for their work packages finishing end of 2023.

<p>TMT WP4 Attendees: Bill Leithead, Michael Muskulus and Nicola Baxter</p>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Design issues to the crossarm – BL says freedom to design this. MM thinks a brace will be more effective. • Adriana and Laurie working on control strategy for pitch loads on tower with neg/pos results. <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ◦ MM will get Adrianna to send some of her results over to BL when they're in. • Blades quite flexible – route hub connection into a cylinder. <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ◦ Displacement but not critical issue. • No need for any extension for this work package at end of 2023.
<p>TMT WP2 Attendees: Bill Leithead, Carlos Simao Ferreira, Beatriz Mendez and Nicola Baxter</p>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • This week a draft of the aeroacoustics deliverable will be submitted for Bill's review. A final version will be submitted next week, with results from higher-resolution simulations. • The work on the aerodynamic benchmark continues, with the paper in an advanced version. • We are continuing with the work on the modelling of wake control and higher-density windfarms with the X-Rotor, with very positive results. This was not part of the original deliverables, and we would like to explore the idea of a small extension to the project so we can complete the work and publish it in the project. Simon is in point to address this with you. • CSF is going to ask for an extension for WP2, not because the deliverables will be late, but regarding getting results published. He will send an email to BL and JC. • Building full scale motor. • CSF will be here for WESC and will meet with Bill during this time, which will be a technical meeting with a visit to labs etc. NB to set up. • BM is looking at mesh / simulations and looking at an increase for correct power. The benchmark for full concept using primary and secondary rotors should be ready in the next couple of weeks and will send over. They recently published with a video of simulations – BM will send over. • Aerodynamic dampening for blades – correlation needed.
<p>TMT WP5 Attendees: Bill Leithead, David Campos Genoa, Olimpo</p>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Power electronic interface – increase to 98%. • Preparing rotary transformer. • Got vessel information from James. • Reza redesigning machine/outer rotor from a magnets point of view.

Anya-Lara and Nicola Baxter			<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Paper accepted for conference in Newcastle (took place last week) and also Japan, Reza attending this. They've now requested a journal paper to be submitted. • Operating conditions 20% swing in frequency with power – can move forward with 28% swing as acceptable but more difficult. • Simulation taking place and working with 20% - looks okay.
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Deliverable/Milestone

Submitted for review	Notes	Who?
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	D2.7	TU Delft
<input type="checkbox"/>	MS23 (extension has been asked for and granted)	UCC

○ **Signature of Project Lead**

Name: William Leithead

Signature:

Date: 19/05/23

○ **Ratification by GE Partner**

In signing off this form, the representative for the GE partner is confirming that the work is of a standard acceptable to industry or will be, should any action requested be completed.

Name: Jordi Jové Bellot

Signature:

Date: 26/05/23

3.5 May 2023

Details of meetings

Meeting	Progress Satisfactory	Progress Unsatisfactory	Notes
<p>TMT WP7/9 Attendees: Bill Leithead, Peter Jamieson, Niall Dunphy, and Nicola Baxter</p>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Everything progressing well as per last meeting in April. • Request gone to EU PO for extension on D7.2. • WindEurope went well with industry stakeholder surveys. Good feedback so far. • Next community engagement is in Donegal, NB attending with UCC. Still to decide where in Europe for one in summer, possibly somewhere in Spain. • WP7.3 - biological scheduling is being done for the summer months. • Life-cycle assessment in underway with collaboration with WP6. • There will be a cross-referenced report on economics for D7.5. • Consider end of project is taken to Deepwind in Jan 2024 but this would mean extending the project for a few months. BL needs to consider this carefully. Otherwise, final event will be in London at Royal College of Engineers.

<p>TMT WP4 Attendees: Bill Leithead, Michael Muskulus, and Nicola Baxter</p>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • MM will get Adrianna to send some of her results over to BL when they're in regarding control strategy for pitch loads. • MM been looking at calculations for crossbar. Not optimum as linear (factor of 2) <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ Concerns with fatigue in bending ○ 2000 tonnes and looking how to reduce this. • Reduction in loads for control • Need to look at costs • BL asked MM to do a sensitivity analysis with a breakdown of all contributions (upper arms, upper wind speed). • Reduce loads by 7-8%? 19m/s (information given by Carlos).
<p>TMT WP2 Attendees: Bill Leithead, Peter Jamieson, Carlos Simoa Ferreira, Beatrix Mendez, Jordi Jové Bellot and Nicola Baxter</p>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Carlos confirmed there will be 2 researchers coming with him to the Consortium meeting in Barcelona. • BM explained that CENER is using the aerodynamic loads and making comparing the benchmark with UoS, Delft and NTNU. <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ They are looking at 2 types of meshing. ○ They expect to have the comparisons for loads completed by the end August for deliverable 2.8 • CSF update included the experimental data that David Beason will present at WESC next week and the report will be ready in a week or 2 and added to SharePoint. • Generally, very happy with results from the benchmark, and have been processing experiments since the new year. <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ Wake explained by 3D model. ○ David is currently building a small model 60x60cm. ○ Good agreement with simulations and calculations ○ Demonstration of wake control coming up. • 4 months extension required for WP2. • CSF kindly updated JJB with where he's at with the latest research using a PowerPoint presentation. • More power with adjustable blades. Positive pitch wake regime with nose in for high wind speeds and negative pitch for low wind speeds.

TMT WP5 Attendees: Bill Leithead, Jordi Jové Bellot, David Campos Genoa	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • DCG updated JJB with some latest information from his research, which included the structure deflection weight. • Regarding rotor transformer and location in tower – NTNU helping assess this work; defining parameter analysis with heat in tower with rotation. • Looked at capability of speed rotations = 375/2 – 8% efficiency at 22-degree angle on secondary rotors.
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Deliverable/Milestone

Submitted for review	Notes	Who?
<input type="checkbox"/>	N/A for this month	

○ **Signature of Project Lead**

Name: William Leithead

Signature:

Date: 16/06/23

○ **Ratification by GE Partner**

In signing off this form, the representative for the GE partner is confirming that the work is of a standard acceptable to industry or will be, should any action requested be completed.

Name: Jordi Jové Bellot

Signature:

Date: 23/06/23

3.6 June 2023

Details of meetings

Meeting	Progress Satisfactory	Progress Unsatisfactory	Notes
<p>TMT WP7/9 Attendees: Niall Dunphy and Nicola Baxter</p>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Industry engagement went well with WESC, week 23rd May, with UCC colleagues gathering information. <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ Stakeholder engagement was online for both the 1st and 2nd years due to the pandemic – UCC will take stock of what information they have and how much more is needed for a 3rd year. They may reach out to GE colleagues during the consortium in Barcelona to get their prospective. • Interviews were carried out for the XROTOR website with many colleagues participating in short videos on their work. • The next community engagement is in Malin Head, Donegal on 15th June. There will be 1 more in Scotland and another in Europe. • The bird tracking results are being gathered with UCC colleague currently out at sea. • ND wondered about the extension to the project? He would like more time for ecological modelling and some economics if possible.

<p>TMT WP4 Attendees: Bill Leithead, Jordi Jové Bellot, Michael Muskulus and Nicola Baxter</p>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • MM updated JJB on what he presented at WESC last week which include using a spreadsheet for jacket calculations to compare with the simulations. This primarily looks at weight and cost. <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ◦ There were 2 errors with previous calculations with the joints for the jacket, but this has been worked out. ◦ There was a weight of 2000t which was too heavy but that’s now down to 60% less with reducing the stressor capacity of the joint. ◦ Strengthening the joints is important and will work in the favour economically. • There is also a spreadsheet calculating the crossbar analysis which confirms cycles. • The geometry of the braces is now closer to the initial preliminary studies done by UoS. • Looking at bearings and unlocking mechanisms. • MM expects results to be finished end of June and then written up. • BL asked for information needed to be able to look at 3-blaced turbine.
<p>TMT WP3 Attendees: Bill Leithead, Jordi Jové Bellot, James Carroll and Nicola Baxter</p>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • BL updated JJB that Adam Stock has left UoS, and another colleague Luis Recalde Camacho replaced him on 1st May. • BL is looking at control of secondary rotors, characteristics and has bottomed out the idea of using them for cooling. • WP3 works closely with WP5, and they have turned the generator inside out. • They’re looking at the aerodynamic modelling etc. and aerodynamic dampening on primary rotor <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Investigating choice of ‘operational strategy’ and improving this. • NTNU needed the dynamic loading on blades reduced a bit and WP3 • Laurie’s parametric study for coning upper part of primary blades showing impact with relative wind speed. No aerodynamic dampening needed. • High wind speeds 90% lower but looking to distribute this 50% each – model of the dynamic dampening needed. • Change the loads by reducing them substantially by end of project.
<p>TMT WP6 Attendees:</p>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • JC used his presentation from WESC to update JJB on the progress of WP6. • There are no flags for end of July deliverables, however a meeting between UCC, JC and BL are required.

Bill Leithead, Jordi Jové Bellot, James Carroll and Nicola Baxter			<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • New analysis is needed for vessels as prices have increased. JJB will ask colleagues in GE if they have any knowledge regarding this. • Fraser is refining analysis with changing a main bearing and the risk of this versus the cost of engineering. <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ Failure rate has been looked at including the main bearing – this is compared to HAWT and removing the need for jack-up vessel. ○ JJB spoke of his concern with main bearing as has large OPEX and CAPEX cost.
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Deliverable/Milestone

Submitted for review	Notes	Who?
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	MS14	NTNU
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	MS17	UoS
<input type="checkbox"/>	D7.7: extension granted to month 32 (end of August)	UCC

○ **Signature of Project Lead**

Name: William Leithead

Signature:

Date: 21/07/23

○ **Ratification by GE Partner**

In signing off this form, the representative for the GE partner is confirming that the work is of a standard acceptable to industry or will be, should any action requested be completed.

Name: Jordi Jové Bellot

Signature:

Date: 28/07/23

3.7 July 2023

Details of meetings

Meeting	Progress Satisfactory	Progress Unsatisfactory	Notes
Monthly catch-up: JC / JJB / NB	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • The extension was discussed. JJB was unable to confirm that GE can continue, although he is positive it'll be okay. • There were a couple of actions from the Consortium meeting that JJB wishes taken forward regarding extreme fatigue and the main bearing. WP5 will update him.
TMT WP meetings	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • No meetings for work packages due to Consortium meeting in Barcelona 27th June, and summer holidays for leads. • Actions from the Consortium meeting will be taken to August TMT WP meetings with leads.

Deliverable/Milestone

Submitted for review	Notes	Who?
☑	D6.2	UCC

○ **Signature of Project Lead**

Name: William Leithead

Signature:

Date: 11/08/23

○ **Ratification by GE Partner**

In signing off this form, the representative for the GE partner is confirming that the work is of a standard acceptable to industry or will be, should any action requested be completed.

Name: Jordi Jové Bellot

Signature:

Date: 18/08/23

3.8 August 2023

Details of meetings

Meeting	Progress Satisfactory	Progress Unsatisfactory	Notes
<p>TMT WP7&9 Attendees: James Carroll, Niall Dunphy, Peter Jamieson and Nicola Baxter</p>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • JD referred to Milestone 33 which is due at the end of September. He didn't ask for an extension on this with EU as it's part of a report due month 36, which hopefully will become month 40. • ND spoke of the Lifecycle Assessment in WP7 and the loss of staff but a calculator will be set up so that numbers can be added as needed for analysis. • PJ spoke of the 5% less materials and industrial processing that needs to be captured in LCA, also the reduction with drive chain stress from suppliers as a positive. PJ and Laurie could contribute to the economics of this. • ND spoke of ongoing economic analysis with Grant and Jack of UoS, they are comparing assumptions with 2 different approaches. • WP9 community outreach in EU may be done online instead of in person. • ND suggested that a holistic paper/case study could be prepared, documenting the process on TRL1-3. JC and BL to consider.

<p>TMT WP5 Attendees: James Carroll, David Campos Genoa and Nicola Baxter</p>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • When the extension has been approved, everyone can continue to work on WP5, this is with the exception of 1 researcher who may get work in industry. Happy for deliverables to move back 4 months. Below are actions from the Consortium meeting in June. • Provide electrical system costs to WP6 for LCoE calculations by end of August. <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ A comparison study with a 5 MW HAWT has been completed by Laurie and Peter and will be send to UCC for the end of the month. • Meeting needed with WP4&5 to discuss air gap. <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ DCG and team met online with Jing Dong to discuss this. It is more mechanical than electrical and less of a problem than first considered. JD is looking at final assessments and new dimensions. She will get a new process for the rotary transformer. This will strengthen the structure as it's not magnetic. Mechanical stiffness should meet less money than other options. A redesign will be necessary one WP4 come back to them with new dimensions. • WP5 to explore technical and economic analysis of slip ring power transfer for comparison with rotary transformer. <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ This work is still ongoing.
<p>TMT WP4 Attendees: James Carroll and Michael Muskulus</p>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • JC gave MM an update on Bill's return and project extension. • WP4 actions from the consortium meeting were discussed. MM reported communication between WP4 and 5 is ongoing related to rotating transformer airgap. MM said CAPEX costs will increase with structural requirements from rotating transformer so further discussions with WP5 will be had related to slip ring airgap as an alternative. • Masses for substructure, tower, cross member, blade etc. planned for end of Sept. • MM will attend the WP2/3/4 meeting on Thursday and will work with his team to be ready to discuss inputs required from WP2.

Deliverable/Milestone

Submitted for review	Notes	Who?
<input type="checkbox"/>	D2.8 – not submitted due to extension	CENER
<input type="checkbox"/>	D4.3 – not submitted due to extension	NTNU

<input type="checkbox"/>	MS20 – not submitted due to extension	UoS
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○ **Signature of Project Lead**

Name: William Leithead

Signature:

Date: 14/09/23

○ **Ratification by GE Partner**

In signing off this form, the representative for the GE partner is confirming that the work is of a standard acceptable to industry or will be, should any action requested be completed.

Name: Jordi Jové Bellot

Signature:

Date: 21/09/23

3.9 September 2023

Details of meetings

Meeting	Progress Satisfactory	Progress Unsatisfactory	Notes
<p>TMT WP7&9 Attendees: Bill Leithead, James Carroll, Niall Dunphy and Nicola Baxter</p>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • WP7: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ◦ There is another social engagement being planned, this will be a small event. ◦ Jack and Grant are working on the systemic analysis, with Jack going to take forward a comparative paper of the 2 studies. UoS top down and UCC bottom up. This will align the differences to take forward. ◦ The environment side of WP7 is finishing at the end of 2023 with the researcher finishing up. They’re leaving processes to be put in place for the extension. This includes a lifecycle assessment model that will be available for the final variables from WP5 to be added. The seabird tracking report will also be completed. ◦ JC pointed out that M23 is due at the end of September for the birdlife – ND will check this. • WP9: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Progress is going well. UCC have some posts to go up on the website. Ongoing collection of publications etc. from all WP’s – NB suggesting another email to all participants as reminder. • Final event – WindEurope at the end of March 2024 is the obvious choice. JC has emailed Simon Watson TU Delft to ask regarding a stand and a room for a couple of hours for a session. <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ◦ Consideration is being made for a less technical overview at the RCE in 2024 using younger researchers to speak at this. Also attending Deepwind 2024 but not necessarily showcasing XROTOR as info was given this year and final results won’t be in by then with extension.
<p>TMT WP5 Attendees: James Carroll, and David Campos Gaona</p>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Slipring analysis is close to complete. Once complete, David to circulate and talk to Laurie about including in his configuration comparison. • David raised point that sliprings will also need increased structural support to reduce movement at point of connection.

			<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • David and team to try determine the max allowable movement from slip ring manufacturer. • David to investigate high cost of power converters in Laurie's cost comparison.
<p>TMT WP2 Attendees: Bill Leithead, James Carroll, Carlos Simoa Ferreira, Beatriz Mendez and Nicola Baxter</p>	☒	☐	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • CSF advised: • The researchers will present the results from the more detailed models to UoS directly. NB to liaise with CSF for a date. • There is a scaled down version of XROTOR which David and Adhyanth will have ready for Feb 2024. They are carrying out longer studies of the wake. • There have been live simulations with models and the benchmark is ready for submission. • The air acoustic experiment will be ready for the end of the project in April 2024. • The aeroelastic model is needed by WP3 for a deliverable. Adhyanth will be asked for the framework and results, which will be delivered inside the project. • BM advised: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ Aerodynamic benchmark was looked at by David and Oscar of CENER with simulations and the results are good, publication to follow shortly. ○ Another model was needed, which David from TU Delft was helping with to compare with CENER. ○ Deliverable end of August is now December with the extension, but BM would hope for end of Oct/Nov. ○ TU Delft continues to supply information to CENER, and this is working well. ○ Control model comparison with ‘benchmark’ paper. • Blades are carbon – 3D printer – shunt and connectors – aerofoils. Aluminium 7cm mode. 1.5m model for wind tunnel and 16W.
<p>TMT WP4 Attendees: Bill Leithead, Michael Muskulus, Jordi Jové Bellot and Nicola Baxter</p>	☒	☐	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • MM update BL: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ Bearing on shaft – issues with airgap on shaft as needs to be <2mm and Jing has revised the 10mm gap which is big and expensive to 0.8. BL commented that traditional take-off should work. JJB voiced his concerns regarding the non-elastic join as this could have any gap as not transferring load from one to another. MM explained the issue is that it keeps rotating. JJB suggesting floating structure and not rigid for rotary transformer.

			<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ Cross-bar is a difficult part, it is also expensive. Drag has a loss of 2-3% at high wind speeds. A student at NTNU is looking at a 4m steel tube as an option for reducing the movement but cables may drag along. It is hoped this research will be ready mid-October. BL pointed out the if the rotary transformer isn't going to work, then that's what get acknowledged. ○ Jacket – substructure – strengthening joints – transition equals jacket assumptions between leg and structure, there is a 20-25% increase in loads from stress. Optimisation needs to be looked at. The design will be ready by end of September. Simplified optimisation of the scaled joint – small stress factors and upscale them on computer. BL commented that this may that it needs to be 3 blades for the jacket costs to decrease. ○ Pile design – needs to be updated but is there similar to what been before? BL What drives loads – ultimate loads for resistance and fatigue not an issue.
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Deliverable/Milestone

Submitted for review	Notes	Who?
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	MS 24 - Bird life empirical data collected	UCC

○ **Signature of Project Lead**

Name: William Leithead

Signature:

Date: 13/10/23

○ **Ratification by GE Partner**

In signing off this form, the representative for the GE partner is confirming that the work is of a standard acceptable to industry or will be, should any action requested be completed.

Name: Jordi Jové Bellot

Signature:

Date: 20/10/23

3.10 October 23

Details of meetings

Meeting	Progress Satisfactory	Progress Unsatisfactory	Notes
<p>TMT WP5 Attendees: Bill Leithead, James Carroll, David Campos-Genoa, Jordi Jose-Bellot and Nicola Baxter</p>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<p>DCG gave an update including:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Initial cost assessment demonstrated cost of power electronics was the largest of the CAPEX in the XROTOR system, which seemed unusual. The price for power electronic converters was revised and the initial cost of 40 USD per KW was corroborated. However, it was noted that this cost was “end product” cost, not raw material. If raw material cost was used instead (just the semiconductors) cost would have reduced to 10 USD per KW. The cost of the rest of the components of the XROTOR such as generators, rotary transformers, etc. was calculated using raw material cost only. So, they appear cheaper when compared with the end product cost of the power electronics. <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ A fairer comparison is needed when assessing the impact of the cost of power electronics in the overall CAPEX of the system. • Regarding the airgap – still working with WP4 who have redesigned the system and shared the results of a 1mm gap in extreme conditions. <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ JJB reiterated the need for the bearing and towers not to be rigid, as they should float. This has been discussed numerous times.

<p>TMT WP2 Attendees: James Carroll, Jordi Jose-Bellot, Carlos-Simao Ferreira, Yan Wu, Beatrix Mendez, Peter Jamieson and Nicola Baxter</p>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Researcher YU presented to the group with an update regarding the noise from a XROTOR. <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ This is very loud at 110db. The data was surprising as the secondary rotas are louder than the primary. The secondary rota has less broadband noise. • BM has new geometry/mass of CFD, and is comparing the results with TU Delft, which she hopes to get back next week. The deliverable will then be written, this is now due at the end of December as per the extension. <p>2nd Meeting:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Action from WP2,3&4 meeting regarding aeroelastic model – CSF has confirmed this will be available at the end of the year so that another WP can take forward. Adhyanth taking forward. <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ Adhyanth also working on the loads and in contact with Michael Muskulus regarding control with fixed pitch. However, if looking at a rotating pitch, this needs to come from UoS. BL agreed to send this over to CSF. • CSF confirmed that their deliverables will be on time. They are writing an additional report regarding the wake to be submitted to EU.
<p>TMT WP7/9 Attendees: James Carroll, Jordi Jose-Bellot, Niall Dunphy, Peter Jamieson and Nicola Baxter</p>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • ND updated the meeting that everything is proceeding as expected. • He agrees to the final event being WindEurope in Bilbao, March 2024 with the possibility of a side event at DeepWind in Trondheim in January 2024. • He will consider what would be needed for a holistic/methodology paper and the need for this. <p>2nd Meeting:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • ND agreed to write a proposal for WindEurope as all agreed this final event should be well organised. • Life Cycle Analysis (LCA) researcher is finishing at the end of November. JC asked if this time could be moved to April to help with end of project. ND will check with Fiona if this is possible. <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ JC asked questions regarding the LCA and level of detail that is required by each WP. ND confirmed that this analysis document it must be filled in and ‘assumptions’ can be made where the outcome is unknown. One sentence explaining the assumption is enough.

			<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ The LCA is needed as its detailed into T7.3 and 6.3 from the Grant agreement as it feeds into the design process. ○ The best way forward is to share what information is available; highlighting what isn't; go to experts to gain information. • JC spoke of TU Delft attendance at 3 x conferences regarding XROTOR for ND to reach out to. • ND will put some notes with a structure of what a holistic paper would look like. He will also find an example paper to send over to UoS.
<p>TMT WP4 Attendees: Bill Leithead, James Carroll, Jordi Jose-Bellot, Michael Muskulus and Nicola Baxter</p>	☒	☐	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • MM and the researchers are working with the final design and optimising this – hopefully 1 more week. The simulations are not working and there are issues with the code. • Researcher Jing Dong has worked on 3 designs for the drive train and submitting these as a journal paper. With a rotary transformer there is no air gap issue so therefore less weight. Hoping for best but cheapest design. • Researcher Adriana Correia da Silva has a working model but there are issues with the length/angle for stress concentrations – all estimated now but no optimised. • The mass on blades is still the same as the feasibility study by UoS. WP6/UCC will take this forward. • It's hard to calculate the bearing masses and cost due to most literature being for HAWTs or using empirical data to draw from to get an idea. MM took the action for JD to get numbers, and a costing from industry. • Discussion around the spreadsheet for LCA with cost of energy analysis to include gas, welding, transporting etc. JC thinks this maybe out with the remit of this research but will check with WP7, Niall Dunphy. • JJB spoke of the designs, models and assumptions with loads and controller. He asked about the impact with the masses/loads and final design. This will be discussed at the WP2, 3 &4 meeting on Thursday. • BL spoke of the final results showing all the tools that have been developed whether it's for a 2 or 3 bladed turbine.
<p>WP6: Attendees:</p>	☒	☐	<p>JC updated the group.</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Next and final deliverable 6.3 is due at the end of Feb 2024.

<p>Bill Leithead, James Carroll, Jordi Jose-Bellot, and Nicola Baxter</p>			<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ Fiona Devoy McAuliffe is due to finish with XROTOR end of Nov. JC asked the TMT if they agreed to him asking if her last 1.5 months can be spread out so that she is available for this deliverable. They agreed. ○ Otherwise, the model has been partially populated and JC will fill this in and write the deliverable. This LCoE model was created and is similar to past EU project work UCC have done. There are some issues with what was sent so far, and JC is working with UCC to work these out. <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • BVG bottom-up approach with no difference between HAWT types on certain things like blades. ○ Suggested getting masses from reference turbines for different types of HAWTs, this hadn't been tried as Fiona more finance background. JC in close contact with UCC. ○ Blade masses from feasibility study by UoS. Work with researcher Laurie Morgan, and David Campos Genoa from WP5 to determine what to use from LM analysis and what to get from post literature / industry quotes from NTNU for bearing costs. Controller costs same at HAWT? Look or investigate what's included in that. <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • JJB asked if the project was analysing failure loads to include in costs; additional device to 'lock the rotor' or 'lock blades' – technology for CAPEX? ○ JC thinks this has been done – will check Fraser Andersons work, and feasibility study for answers. ○ BL checking deliverables and will ask MM regarding design for dropping mechanism of the main bearing.
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Deliverable/Milestone

Submitted for review	Notes	Who?
<input type="checkbox"/>	<p>N/A for this month</p>	

- **Signature of Project Lead**

Name: William Leithead

Signature:

Date: 17/11/23

○ **Ratification by GE Partner**

In signing off this form, the representative for the GE partner is confirming that the work is of a standard acceptable to industry or will be, should any action requested be completed.

Name: Jordi Jové Bellot

Signature:

Date: 24/11/23

3.11 November 2023

Details of meetings

Meeting	Progress Satisfactory	Progress Unsatisfactory	Notes
TMT WP5 Attendees: Bill Leithead, David Campos	☒	☐	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • 2 papers have been submitted to IET Renewable Energy Generation and DeepWind, which demonstrate the rotary transformer. <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ PhD student Yang Teng will deploy a 1KW scaled down experiment of the rotary transformer system.

<p>Gaona and Nicola Baxter</p>			<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • The machine design will be reviewed to verify the assumption that XROTOR secondary generators cost around 10 times less than their direct-drive counterparts. <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ There will be trade-offs – 99% efficiency; 98% costs cut ○ More are than needed for least dissipation. ○ Diameter of rotor will cut costs and there is a range of options for requirements. ○ Costings include consistent retail / cost (like for like). ○ Optimisation – will reuse numbers. ○ Reducing power factor. ○ Rated by 1 secondary rotor working it and taking up the whole power.
<p>TMT WP4: Attendees: Bill Leithead, Michael Muskulus, James Carroll and Nicola Baxter</p>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • MM been looking into the lockdown design but is finding costs hard to get. Regardless of it will be very expensive. He took down the action again to ask JD to help him get material and manufacturing costs and reach out to industry for this. • Still to check sideways loading with scales and distance. • JD writing up jacket design for the deliverable. It’s still a bit heavy and MM must go through the calculations before submission. • BL to send MM and WP2 the operational strategy with wind speed and pitch angles for them both to take this forward.
<p>TMT WP7/9: Attendees: Bill Leithead, Niall Dunphy, James Carroll and Nicola Baxter</p>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • ND discussed the Holistic Paper – he has 2 suggestions on who to take this forward with: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ Journal – Research for Admin. Consider: How this project came together – All WP’s. XROTOR is different – TMT meetings. The culture of the PM is different and positive. ○ Open Research Europe – online – public review through EC. • The final event was discussed at WindEurope: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ To consider: comms - invites - what're we going to say externally - what's our tag for final event ○ Tell a story - narrative ○ Posters with technology (not necessarily by WPs), and speakers non-tech ○ Loop quality video version of XROTOR - windfarm / boats to scale / animate ○ Video regarding XROTOR - 5 mins - Bill and/or work package leads • ND asked BL to think about what UoS would like on the legacy website – what stays? • Grant and Jack have sent their 1st draft to UCC of the Top-down comparative paper of economics.

<p>TMT WP2: Bill Leithead, James Carroll, Carlos Simoa Ferreira, Jordi Jové Bellot, Beatriz Mendez and Nicola Baxter</p>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Deliverable due from CENER on 18th December to UoS to check and submit. BM spoke of the comparisons that worked well and the report with start to be written after a meeting tomorrow. This is the last of the work with CENER. • CENER have an abstract for DeepWind, which is a joint paper with TU Delft. • David Bensason and Adhyanth Giri Ajay have oral and poster presentations at Torque. • Simulations will be submitted to Journals by the end of April and beyond. • The aeroelastic model is still on schedule for the end of this year and David is going to do more work in the wind tunnel in the New Year. • CSF agreed that a summary paper of WP2 with UoS is a good idea as unique project management. <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ This will be discussed further at the EMG meeting. • Aeroacoustics – not keen to re-mesh, and the report will be ready by end of February by David B. <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ This will consider getting the tower to work; explore fixed pitched; and improve energy capture with tightly spaced wind farm. ○ CFD comparison – too early to say.
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Deliverable/Milestone

Submitted for review	Notes	Who?
<input type="checkbox"/>	N/A for this month	

○ **Signature of Project Lead**

Name: William Leithead

Signature:

Date: 18/12/23

○ **Ratification by GE Partner**

In signing off this form, the representative for the GE partner is confirming that the work is of a standard acceptable to industry or will be, should any action requested be completed.

Name: Jordi Jové Bellot

Signature:

Date: 20/12/23

3.12 December 2023

Details of meetings

Meeting	Progress Satisfactory	Progress Unsatisfactory	Notes
<p>TMT WP5 Attendees: Bill Leithead, James Carroll, David Campos-Genoa and Nicola Baxter</p>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • DCG explained his team have come up with new solutions for lower costs for the powertrain. They relaxed some of the constraints e.g. weight and efficiency. Looking at a single generator the material costs are a third of original costs. It is cheaper to use sliprings than consider rotating transformer. <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ BL asked if they could select a few options with different radius etc. to show the differences. ○ DCG with get the power convertors to JC for WP6. • A paper has been submitted to DeepWind showing the control at different costs, which has been accepted with Seyed hoping to travel to deliver this abstract to the conference. • They have a deliverable at the end of February 2024 and a Milestone at the end of April 2024.

<p>TMT WP6 Attendees: Bill Leithead, James Carroll, and Nicola Baxter</p>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • CoE inputs – focusing on turbine only. • Fiona in UCC is using her hours for 2024 with the model created and partially populated. • WP3 controller cost similar to traditional HAWTs. • Capital costs v O&M costs. • Can be conservative with tower costs as shorter/similar than traditional HAWT. • Clear communication in report than exemplar turbine will lower cost of energy. • WP5 Comment rotating transformer but going with sliprings. Costs for drive train ready early 2024.
<p>TMT WP4 Attendees: Bill Leithead, James Carroll, Michael Muskulus Jordi Jové Bellot, Peter Jamieson and Nicola Baxter</p>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Adriana is working on the jacket; it has come down a bit in weight at 2888ton. • All with safety factors. Added piles needed to be stronger and lighter. • Needs to be written up and published. • There is no comparison with HAWT for this depth of 50m out at sea. • Looking at loads, fatigue was seen as most important detail. High stress with mud brace. The fatigue is caused by big load cycles. • Main bearing costs – nothing from manufacturer. Looked at older cost models for evaluating system cost but it's very higher at €1.2m but this was for a NREL model which was much bigger. Nothing yet for main bearing exchanges – still working on it. • Re tower costs – increased loads are more expensive. With thickness increase by approx. 30%. Bearing needs to be high-up from the sea, otherwise shaft is too costly.
<p>TMT WP7/9 Attendees: James Carroll, Niall Dunphy and Nicola Baxter</p>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Dissemination and Communication, final document completed. • DeepWind Journals with go towards KPI's. • It's too late to get a stand at WindEurope, these spaces sold out very quickly. ND and colleagues will attend and have informal talks with attendees at conference/trade fair. • Social media has been stepped up with link to website, and twitter posts. Islay info going onto website. <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ Knowledge exchange – newsletter, social media and website

Deliverable/Milestone

Submitted for review	Notes	Who?
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<p>The detailed design deliverable is for NTNU to document a final design that is considered best possible, according to the</p>	<p>WP4</p>

	specific assumptions and methods described in the design basis deliverable D5.1.	
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	Comparison of CFD computations and experimental results	WP2

○ **Signature of Project Lead**

Name: William Leithead

Signature:

Date: 19/01/24

○ **Ratification by GE Partner**

In signing off this form, the representative for the GE partner is confirming that the work is of a standard acceptable to industry or will be, should any action requested be completed.

Name: Jordi Jové Bellot

Signature:

Date: 26/01/24

4 Year 4

4.1 January 2024

Details of meetings

Meeting	Progress Satisfactory	Progress Unsatisfactory	Notes
TMT WP2 Attendees: Bill Leithead, James Carroll, Carlos Simoa Ferreira and Jordi Jové Bellot.	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Discussion on final deliverable progress • Final event input and project reporting
TMT WP7/9 Attendees: Bill Leithead, James Carroll, Niall Dunphy and Jordi Jové Bellot	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Discussion on final deliverable progress • Final event input and project reporting
TMT WP5 Attendees: Bill Leithead, James Carroll, David Campos- Genoa and Jordi Jové Bellot	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Discussion on final deliverable progress • Final event input and project reporting

<p>TMT WP4 Attendees: Bill Leithead, James Carroll, Michael Muskulus and Jordi Jové Bellot</p>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Discussion on final deliverable progress • Final event input and project reporting
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Deliverable/Milestone

Submitted for review	Notes	Who?
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	D3.4 extension granted by PO for April 2024	UoS
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	D4.4 Design verification study	NTNU
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	D7.13 extension granted by PO for March 2024	TU Delft

○ **Signature of Project Lead**

Name: William Leithead

Signature:

Date: 16/02/24

○ **Ratification by GE Partner**

In signing off this form, the representative for the GE partner is confirming that the work is of a standard acceptable to industry or will be, should any action requested be completed.

Name: Jordi Jové Bellot

Signature:

Date: 23/02/24

4.2 February 2024

Details of meetings

Meeting	Progress Satisfactory	Progress Unsatisfactory	Notes
TMT WP6 Attendees: Bill Leithead, James Carroll and Jordi Jové Bellot	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Discussion on final deliverable progress • Final event input and project reporting
TMT WP2 Attendees: Bill Leithead, James Carroll, Carlos Simoa Ferreira and Jordi Jové Bellot.	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Discussion on final deliverable progress • Final event input and project reporting

<p>TMT WP7/9 Attendees: Bill Leithead, James Carroll, Niall Dunphy and Jordi Jové Bellot</p>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Discussion on final deliverable progress • Final event input and project reporting
<p>TMT WP5 Attendees: Bill Leithead, James Carroll, David Campos- Genoa and Jordi Jové Bellot</p>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Discussion on final deliverable progress • Final event input and project reporting
<p>TMT WP4 Attendees: Bill Leithead, James Carroll, Michael Muskulus and Jordi Jové Bellot</p>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Discussion on final deliverable progress • Final event input and project reporting

2. Deliverable/Milestone

Submitted for review	Notes	Who?
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	D2.9 CFD simulations of noise from a full XROTOR	TU Delft
<input type="checkbox"/>	D3.1 extension granted by PO for March 2024	UoS
<input type="checkbox"/>	D3.5 extension granted by PO for April 2024	UoS
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	D5.3 Control systems for maximum power capture and provision of frequency support	UoS

<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	D6.3 CoE of existing turbines modelled and compared to X-Rotor CoE	UCC
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○ **Signature of Project Lead**

Name: William Leithead

Signature:

Date: 15/03/24

○ **Ratification by GE Partner**

In signing off this form, the representative for the GE partner is confirming that the work is of a standard acceptable to industry or will be, should any action requested be completed.

Name: Jordi Jové Bellot

Signature:

Date: 22/03/24

4.3 March 2024

Details of meetings

Meeting	Progress Satisfactory	Progress Unsatisfactory	Notes
TMT WP3 (7th) Attendees: Bill Leithead, James Carroll and Jordi Jové Bellot	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Discussion on final deliverable progress • Final event input and project reporting
TMT WP5 Attendees: Bill Leithead, James Carroll, David Campos-Genoa and Jordi Jové Bellot	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Discussion on final deliverable progress • Final event input and project reporting

Deliverable/Milestone

Submitted for review	Notes	Who?
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	D3.1 Definition of operational strategy	UoS
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	D7.8 Final system-wide assessment on impact on jobs	UCC
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	D7.13 Environmental noise assessment	TU Delft

○ **Signature of Project Lead**

Name: William Leithead

Signature:

Date: 26/04/24

○ **Ratification by GE Partner**

In signing off this form, the representative for the GE partner is confirming that the work is of a standard acceptable to industry or will be, should any action requested be completed.

Name: Jordi Jové Bellot

Signature:

Date: 30/04/24

4.4 April 2024

Details of meetings

Meeting	Progress Satisfactory	Progress Unsatisfactory	Notes
TMT WP7/9 Attendees:	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • ND will have a draft of D7.4 in next week but will have some information to add in from an online workshop that has still to take place.

James Carroll, Niall Dunphy and Nicola Baxter			<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • The LCA model is nearly complete with all the data in from WP's. This will be available to the PO as necessary. • ND will be able to send over a draft of D7.12 next week. • Some work to be some with the webinars recorded in Bilbao at the final event. This will go up on YouTube and then linked to the website. If the recordings aren't great, PhD students from each WP may be asked to present the final work, which can be recorded. • ND happy to liaise with JC regarding D9.6 and gave some pointers on how best to take this forward.
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Deliverable/Milestone

Submitted for review	Notes	Who?
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	D3.4 Controller for X-Rotor	UoS
<input type="checkbox"/>	D3.5 Performance assessment	UoS
<input type="checkbox"/>	D1.6 Final project summary report to EC	UoS
<input type="checkbox"/>	MS2 Periodic status report submitted and approved	UoS
<input type="checkbox"/>	MS18 Control system for maximum power extraction	UoS
<input type="checkbox"/>	D7.4 Year 3 report on workshops and design recommendations	UCC
<input type="checkbox"/>	D7.12 Noise modelling, marine mammal and seabird interaction recommendation	UCC
<input type="checkbox"/>	MS25 Monthly technical report	UoS
<input type="checkbox"/>	MS26 XROTOR development workshop	UoS
<input type="checkbox"/>	MS27 Project results ratified by OEM	GE
<input type="checkbox"/>	MS28 Technology roadmap developed	UoS
<input type="checkbox"/>	D8.1 Monthly report	GE
<input type="checkbox"/>	D8.2 X-Rotor Development workshop	UoS

<input type="checkbox"/>	D8.3 Overall project results ratified by OEM	UoS
<input type="checkbox"/>	D8.4 Technology roadmap developed	UoS
<input type="checkbox"/>	D8.5 Final report on Feasibility of the X-Rotor concept	UoS
<input type="checkbox"/>	D8.6 X-Rotor Review Report	UoS
<input type="checkbox"/>	D9.6 Final comms and dissemination delivery	UoS

- **Signature of Project Lead**

Name: William Leithead

Signature:

Date: 26/04/24

- **Ratification by GE Partner**

In signing off this form, the representative for the GE partner is confirming that the work is of a standard acceptable to industry or will be, should any action requested be completed.

Name: Jordi Jové Bellot

Signature:

Date: 30/04/24

Conclusion

The signed off monthly reports that make up this deliverable evidence the fact that GE were involved in the technical management of this research throughout the XROTOR project. Whilst the detail in the monthly reports may be difficult to follow as standalone outputs, the purpose of this deliverable is to demonstrate the regular involvement and signing off of work from a wind turbine OEM. The involvement of GE ensured the work carried out in this research project was completed to a level that was acceptable by a leading wind turbine manufacturer.